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ETHOSOME: EMERGING TRENDS AND APPLICATIONS IN TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Ethosomal drug delivery systems have numerous applications in the veterinary, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical industries. Several passive and active procedures have been developed to improve the skin's permeability for transdermal drug delivery. The ethanol action and the ethosome effect on the stratum corneum lipid bilayer are involved in the penetration mechanism of ethosomal formulations. Considering that ethanol was used to prepare the ethanol formulation, the vesicles' deformability is boosted. Ethosomes, as opposed to conventional liposomal formulations, enhance medication distribution to the skin in both occlusive and non-occlusives situations. Using ethanol as a carrier, the drug is entrapped into the epidermal membrane. The drug enters the receptor compartment during in vitro skin permeation experiments and in MT-2 cells. In addition, ethanol is used to deliver the drug via the skin or the skin membrane. In this review, we provide an overview of the current research progress in the field of ethanol-based delivery systems.

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INTRODUCTION

Skin is one of the largest and easiest organs in the human body which has several benefits when used as a medication delivery system compared to conventional drug delivery methods, such as reduced variations in plasma medication levels, avoidance due to digestive issues and first-pass drug metabolism, as well as elevated patient adherence. The outermost layer of the skin, known as the stratum corneum (SC), is layered with the dermis and epidermis within. Layers of skin beneath these are hair follicles, sweat glands, and fibroblasts scattered throughout that originate from the blood supply of the dermis. Because the stratum corneum is the strongest barrier to passage, the skin provides an excellent barrier to molecule movement. Majority of medications, with the exception of lipophilic and low molecular weight medications [1]

Numerous techniques have been researched to increase chemical skin penetration, including iontophoresis, sonophoresis, electroporation, microneedles, and many more raise the transdermal transport's effectiveness [2] the first generation elastic lipid vesicular carrier, known as transfersomes was presented by Cevc in 1992. It was mostly composed of an edge activator (non-ionic) with phospholipids supplement.[3,4] These elastic vesicles have been created using phospholipids, ethanol, bile salts, and several surfactants.[5]

Ethosomes are liposomes that are ethanolic. Ethosomes are noninvasive drug delivery vehicles that allow medications to enter the systemic circulation and/or deeply penetrate the skin's layers [6] drug delivery vehicles that are noninvasive and allow medication to enter the systemic circulation or deep skin layers. These pliable, supple vesicles are designed to improve the delivery of active substances. Phospholipids, such as phosphatidylcholine, are the primary Constituents large amounts of water and ethanol, phosphatidylserine, and phosphatidic acid.

Lipid vesicles known as ethosomes are made up of phospholipids, water, and relatively high concentrations of alcohol (ethanol and isopropyl alcohol) [7]

Touitou and her colleagues created ethosomes for the first time in 1997. Ethosomes are pliable, soft lipid vesicles that are primarily made of phospholipids and a comparatively high concentration of alcohol (20-45 percent) and water. Concentrations of phospholipids with different chemical structures, such as phosphatidyl choline and phosphatidyl ethanolamine, range from 0.5-10%. Several passive and active procedures have been developed to improve the skin's permeability for transdermal drug delivery. suggested, including vesicles, penetration enhancers, electroporation, supersaturated systems, iontophoresis, employing jet injectors and microneedles, phonophoresis, etc. [8-10]. The ethosomes are vesicular carriers made of phospholipids that are hydroalcoholic or hydro/alcoholic/glycolic, with the concentration of alcohols or their mixture being reasonably elevated. Potential phospholipid contents in the ethosomes including phosphatidylcholine (PC), which has a variety of chemical structures, PC hydrogenated, PA (phosphatidic acid), phosphoinoserine (PS), ethanolamine (PE), and phosphatidylserine The substances phosphatidylglycerol (PPG), phosphatidylinositol (PI), ethanol (or isopropyl alcohol), hydrogenated PC, and Propylene glycol (or other glycols) combined with water..[11]

Composition of ethosomes

The primary components of ethosomes are phospholipids (phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylserine and phosphatidic acid), along with a significant amount of water and ethanol. The percentages of the nonaqueous phase range from 22% to 70% [12,13] either isopropyl alcohol or ethanol could be the type of alcohol. Frequently added to dyes or amphiphilic fluorescent probes include D-289, Rhodamine-123, fluorescence isothiocyanate (FITC), and 6-carboxy fluorescence ethosomes in a study of characterization. [14] It is used in the range of 0.5–10% w/w. cholesterol in ranges of concentrations .It is also possible to add 0.1–1% to the preparation. Among the glycols, ethanol and isopropyl alcohol typically propylene glycol is utilized, which could be between 20 and 50% in the finished product 15]

Structure of ethosomes

Figure No: 01 structure of ethosomes.

Mechanism of drug penetration

Ethosomes have more drug penetration than liposomes, which is their primary benefit. It is unclear how drugs are absorbed from ethosomes. Two simultaneous processes of the ethanol action and the ethosome effect on the stratum corneum lipid bilayer are involved in the ethosome penetration mechanism. Considering that ethanol was used to prepare the ethosome, the vesicles' deformability is boosted. The highly flexible vesicles have the ability to follow the structure of the disrupted stratum corneum, ultimately releasing medication into the skin's deeper layers. [16] The drug absorption probably occurs in following two phases:

Figure No : 02 drug penetration of ethosome.

Ref: SreekanthNama. Dr ETHOSOMES: A NOVEL DRUG CARRIER FOR TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY MARCH 2013

1. Ethanol effect

As it penetrates the skin, ethanol improves penetration. Its penetration-enhancing effect's mechanism is widely recognized. The fluidity of cell membrane lipids is increased and the density of the lipid multilayer of the cell membrane is decreased when ethanol penetrates into intercellular lipids.

2. Ethosome effect

Skin permeability increases as a result of the ethanol in ethosomes increasing the lipid fluidity of the cell membrane. As a result, the ethosomes enter the deep layers of the skin with great ease, where they combine with skin lipids to release medication into the skin's deep layers. [17]

Advantages of ethosomes

1. Compared to other complex drug delivery methods like phonophoresis and iontophoresis, this method is straightforward.
2. Ethosomal drug delivery systems have numerous applications in the veterinary, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical industries.
3. A high level of patient compliance is achieved when the ethosomal medication is administered in a semisolid form, such as a gel or cream. [18]
4. ethosomal system can be immediately commercialized and is non-invasive and passive.
5. Low risk profile: Since the toxicological profiles of the ethosomal components are well-documented in the scientific literature, there is no significant risk of drug development due to technology.
6. Market attractiveness for goods using exclusive technology. Ethosome production is relatively easy to produce and doesn't require a lot of sophisticated technical equipment [19]
7. Ethosomes, as opposed to conventional liposomes, enhance medication distribution to the skin in both occlusive and non-occlusive situations.
8. Many medications have greater stability and solubility when compared to traditional vesicles.
9. Comparatively smaller in size than traditional vesicles [20]
10. Compared to other drugs, drugs encapsulated in ethosomes with distinct physicochemical properties and molecular diameters exhibit a significant degree of penetration carriers of nanoscale.
11. Increased drug penetration through the skin for transdermal medication administration.
12. Non-toxic raw materials are used in its formulation.
13. The greatest transdermal flow demonstrated by ethosomes facilitates medication penetration into the skin's deeper layers.
14. Because of extensive study the scientific literature contains well-evaluated and recorded toxicity profiles of the ethosome components; hence, the ethosome technology lacks a widespread medication danger of development [21]

Disadvantages of ethosomes

1. The purpose of ethosomal administration is often to provide delayed, persistent medication delivery rather than to provide quick bolus-type drug input.
 2. Drugs that need high blood levels cannot be delivered; they can only be used in small doses (10 mg or less per day).
 3. For the medicine to be absorbed through the skin, its molecular size needs to be appropriate.
 4. If shell locking proves to be insufficient, the ethosomes may agglomerate and disintegrate upon transfer into water.
 5. Excipients and enhancers in drug delivery systems can cause skin irritation or dermatitis.
 6. Certain skin types may not respond well to adhesive.
 7. Perhaps not cost-effective
 8. Product loss during the conversion of water media from organic media.
 9. The medicine must be sufficiently soluble in both lipophilic and aqueous conditions in order to enter the systemic circulation and cutaneous microcirculation [22-25]
- Overall, the objective of the review article is to enhance understanding of ethanol-based delivery systems, particularly ethosomal drug delivery systems, and to stimulate further research and innovation in this important area of drug delivery technology.

Methods of preparation of ethosomes

Ethosomes can be prepared and formulated by following methods.

Cold method

This is most common and widely using method for preparation of ethosomal formulation. In this procedure, phospholipid, medication, and other lipid components are dissolved in ethanol at room temperature in a covered jar while being vigorously stirred using blender adding propylene glycol or another polyol during agitating. In a water bath, this combination is heated to 30°C. In a different vessel, water heated to 30°C is added to the combination, which is then agitated in a closed dish for five minutes. The extrusion technique or probe sonication can be used to reduce the ethosomal formulation's vesicle size to the desired degree. Care should be made to keep the ethanol from evaporating during the whole procedure. In conclusion, the mixture is refrigerated for storage. [26]

Figure No: 03 cold method.

Ref:Manoj Kumar Mishra Ethosomes: A novel vesicular carrier system for therapeutic applications january 2018

Hot method

This process involves heating phospholipid in a water bath at 40°C until a colloidal solution is produced. The phospholipid is then disseminated in the water. Ethanol and propylene glycol are combined and heated to 40°C in a different container. The organic phase is introduced to the aqueous phase once both combinations have reached 40°C. Depending on whether the medication is hydrophilic or hydrophobic, it dissolves in either water or ethanol. Probe sonication or extrusion methods can be used to reduce the ethosomal formulation's vesicle size to the desired degree [27]

Figure No: 04 hot method.

Ref: Mohammed Misbah UI Haq. Ethosomes as Novel Vesicular Carrier: An Overview January 2021

Classic method

The medication and phospholipid are dissolved in ethanol and heated in a water bath to $30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The lipid is mixed with a fine stream of double-distilled water, while continuously stirring at 700 rpm in a closed cylinder. With the use of a hand extruder and a polycarbonate membrane, the resultant vesicle solution is homogenized over three cycles [28].

Various methods of characterisation of ethosomes

1. vesicle shape

Ethosomes can be seen through the use of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Electron microscopy visualization indicates that ethosomal formulation showed vesicular 300–400 nm in diameter is the structure. The particles appear to be acceptable, as seen by the irregular rounded form of them.

2. Vesicle size and zeta potential

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) employing photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS) and an automated inspection system can measure particle size and zeta potential.

3. Drug entrapment

The ultracentrifugation technique may be used to test the drug's entrapment efficiency in ethosomes. The vesicles are separated in a 4°C -maintained high-speed cooling centrifuge at 20,000 rpm for 90 minutes. Ratio of entrapment = $\frac{\text{Real content}}{\text{Theoretical content}} \times 100$

DE: Drug content in the ethosomal sediment

DT: The amount of drug utilized theoretically to make the formulation (equivalent to the amount of drug in the sediment and supernatant liquid) [29]

4. Transition temperature

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) may be used to find the transition temperature of the vesicular lipid system terms

5. Drug content

The UV spectrophotometer may be used to determine the drug content of the ethosomes. A modified high performance liquid chromatography approach may also be used to quantify this.

6. Stability studies

The size and shape of the vesicles can be evaluated over time to ascertain their stability. DLS calculates the mean size, while TEM detects structural alterations.

7. Surface tension measurement

A Du Nouy ring tensiometer may be used to measure the surface tension activity of a medication in an aqueous solution using the ring technique.

8. Skin permeation studies

Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) can be used to assess the ethosomal preparation's capacity to pierce the epidermal layers. [30]

EVALUATION TEST

A. Filter membrane-Vesicle interaction study by scanning electron microscopy

The membrane with a pore size of 50 nm is filtered by applying 0.2 mL of vesicle solution, and it is then placed in diffusion cells. The filter was placed in contact with phosphate buffer saline solution (pH 6.5) on its lower side, while its top side was exposed to the air after an hour the filters were taken out and cleaned with Karnovsky's fixative at 4°C for the next day. The filters were then dehydrated using ethanol solutions varying in volume (30%, 50%, 70%, 90%, 95%, and 100% v/v in water) in order to prepare them for SEM investigations. Gold coating was applied to the filters, and they were then inspected under a SEM (Leica, Bensheim, Germany).

B. Vesicle-skin interaction study by TEM and SEM

Animals were prepared into ultra-thin slices (Ultra cut, Vienna, Austria), gathered onto formvar-coated grids, and studied using a transmission electron microscope. The skin slices were dehydrated, mounted on stubs using adhesive tape, and coated with gold palladium alloy using a fine coat ion sputter coater for SEM examination. A scanning electron microscope was used to examine the sections.

C. Skin permeation studies

Using a knife, the abdomen skin was removed from the underlying connective tissue, and the test animals' (rats') hair was carefully clipped short (<2 mm) using scissors. The diffusion cell's and the receptor cell's effective permeation areas were 1.0 cm² and 10 mL, respectively. A constant 32°C ± 1°C was maintained. At 1-, 2-, 4-, 8-, 12-, 16-, 20-, & 24 hour time intervals, samples (0.5 ml) were removed through the diffusion cell's sampling port and examined using an HPLC (high performance liquid chromatography) test.

D. Vesicle-Skin interaction study by fluorescence microscopy

As per the protocol used for the TEM and SEM study, fluorescence microscopy was conducted. The cytotoxic dose 50 (CD50) that caused a 50% decrease in absorbance at 540 nm was used to express cytotoxicity.

E. Drug uptake studies

The drug was taken up by MT-2 cells (1×10⁶ cells/mL) in 24-well plates (Corning Inc.) with 100 µL of RPMI medium added. Drug uptake was assessed by analyzing the drug content using an HPLC assay after cells were incubated with 100 µL of the drug solution in PBS [pH 7.4], ethosomal formulation, or commercial formulation.

F. Statistical analysis

ANOVA was used to test the statistical significance of all the generated data, and then a studentized range test was performed. PRISM (GraphPad, Version 2.01, San Diego, CA) software was used to interpret the results with a fixed confidence limit of P < .05.

G. HPLC Assay

The HPLC assay was used to measure the amount of drug that entered the receptor compartment during in vitro skin permeation experiments and in MT-2 cells. [31, 32]

APPLICATION OF ETHOSOMES

Transdermal delivery of hormones

Hormones administered orally are linked to issues such as high first pass metabolism, low oral bioavailability, and dose-dependent side effects. It is well known that the chance of treatment failure rises with each missed pill.

Pilosebaceous targeting

The role of sebaceous glands and hair follicles in percutaneous drug delivery is becoming more widely acknowledged. Minoxidil, a lipid-soluble medication, is applied topically to the scalp via pilosebaceous delivery to treat baldness. Specifically to treat conditions involving the follicles, like alopecia or acne. [33]

Delivery of problematic drug molecules

Transdermal delivery is a preferable option for the oral administration of large biogenic molecules like insulin, peptides, and proteins because the GIT tract completely breaks them down. However, peptides, proteins, and insulin have poor penetration when applied topically in conventional transdermal formulation. The permeation and therapeutic efficacy of ethosomes that contain the aforementioned molecules are greatly increased. [34]

Transcellular delivery

Using CLSM and FACS techniques, the study showed improved intracellular uptake of erythromycin, DNA, and bacitracin in various cell lines. When compared to the commercial formulation, ethosomes MT-2 cell line demonstrated superior cellular uptake of the anti-HIV drugs zidovudine and lamivudine, indicating that ethosomes represent an appealing clinical alternative for anti-HIV therapy. [35]

Delivery of anti-parkinsonism agent:

THP (trihexyphenidyl hydrochloride) was given an ethosomal formulation and its delivery was compared to that of a traditional liposomal formulation. THP is a Parkinson disease treatment medication that blocks M1 muscarinic receptors. The application of ethosomal-THP formulation for improved Parkinson disease management was suggested by the results, which also showed improved skin penetration potential

Delivery of HIV drugs

Long-term use of an effective antiretroviral therapy is necessary, and it has significant side effects. To maintain the anticipated anti-AIDS effect, there needs to be an adequate zero order delivery of zidovudine, a powerful antiviral agent. Acyclovir formulations have a higher percentage of abortive lesions and shorter healing times, indicating high therapeutic efficacy. [36]

Delivery of anti-arthritis drug

Anti-arthritis medication delivered topically is preferable due to its site-specific administration, which also solves the issue with traditional oral therapy.

Cosmaceutical application of ethosomes

Applying ethosomes to cosmetics has the benefit of improving transdermal permeation, particularly in elastic forms, in addition to increasing the stability of the cosmetic chemicals and reducing skin irritation from irritating cosmetic chemicals. To achieve these benefits of elastic vesicles for cosmetic applications, it is necessary to take into account the sizes and compositions of the vesicles. [37]

Marketed products of ethosomes:

The ethosomes technology started to become commercially viable in 2000. The ethosomes product was developed by just two companies [38-40]

Table No: 01 marketed products of ethosomes.

NAME OF PRODUCT	INDICATION	MANUFACTURER
Decorin cream	Anti-aging cream,treating ,repairing,and delaying the visible aging of the skin including wrinkle lines.	Genome cosmetics
Nanominox	First minoxidil containing product,which uses ethosomes,contains 4% minoxidil,well-known hair growth promoter that must be metabolized by sulfation to the active compound	Germany
Skin genuity	Powerful cellulite buster, reduces orange pee	Nottingham,UK
Supravir cream	For the treatment of herpes virus	Trima,Israel

Ref: Anil Pethe ,Ethosomes.2018,july 24.

Future perspective:

Therefore, it stands to reason that ethosomal formulations have a bright future in terms of efficiently delivering bioactive agents via the skin or transdermal membrane. The noninvasive delivery of small, medium, and large sized drug molecules is made possible by ethosomes. This conclusion is supported by data from the initial clinical trial of acyclovir ethosomal formulation. It is very simple to prepare ethosomal formulation in multiliter quantities. The stratum corneum serves as the primary barrier layer preventing drug penetration in transdermal delivery. More research in this field will enable physicians to better regulate drug release in vivo and increase the efficacy of the therapy. Therefore, it stands to reason that ethosomal formulations have a bright future in terms of efficiently delivering bioactive agents via the skin or transdermal membrane.

CONCLUSION

It is simple to conclude that ethosomes have superior skin penetration capabilities compared to liposomes. When compared to transdermal and dermal delivery, ethosomes have more advantages. They are the non-invasive drug delivery vehicles that make it possible for medications to enter the deep layers of the skin and ultimately enter the bloodstream. Ethosomes can be modified for improved skin penetration of active medications and are known for their ease of preparation, safety, and effectiveness. Drugs that are cationic, hydrophilic, or contain proteins or peptides have all been tested to be encapsulated in ethosomes. Therefore, ethosomal formulations have a bright future in the efficient transdermal delivery of bioactive substances.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical matter:

NIL

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